

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D4.6 – iHelp DSS suite with visual analytics I

WP4 Knowledge Management and Utilisation in the
iHelp Platform

Dissemination Level: Public
Document type: Report
Version: 1.0.0
Date: December 28, 2021

The project iHelp has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for research, technological development, and demonstration under grant agreement no 101017441.

Document Details

Project Number	101017441
Project Title	iHelp - Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records
Title of deliverable	iHelp DSS suite with visual analytics I
Work package	WP4
Due Date	31/12/2021
Submission Date	28/12/2021
Start Date of Project	January 1, 2021
Duration of project	36 months
Main Responsible Partner	UPM
Deliverable nature	Public
Author name(s)	Ainhoa Azqueta (UPM), Marta Patiño (UPM), Oscar García (ICE)
Reviewer name(s)	Giorgos Giotis (ATC), Harm op den Akker (iSPRINT)

Document Revision History

Version History			
Version	Date	Author(s)	Changes made
0.1	2021-09-29	Ainhoa Azqueta (UPM)	Initial version and Table of Contents
0.2	2021-11-30	Ainhoa Azqueta (UPM)	Contents provided
0.3	2021-12-03	Marta Patiño (UPM)	Contents for several sections
0.4	2021-12-22	Giorgos Giotis (ATC)	1 st Internal Review
0.5	2021-12-22	Harm op den Akker (iSPRINT)	2 nd Internal Review
0.6	2021-12-23	Ainhoa Azqueta (UPM)	New version
0.7	2021-12-26	Marta Patiño (UPM)	Final Review and update
0.9	2021-12-27	Pavlos Kranas (LXS)	Quality check
1.0	2021-12-28	Dimosthenis Kyriazis (UPRC)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive summary	4
1 Introduction.....	5
1.1 Objective of the Deliverable	5
1.2 Structure of the Deliverable	5
2 Clinical DSS Suite	6
2.1 Overview.....	6
2.2 Overall Objectives.....	6
2.3 Internal Architecture	6
2.3.1 User Interaction with the DSS	7
2.4 Related Work.....	8
2.5 Positioning and Relation with Other Components.....	10
3 Workflow Interface	11
3.1 iHelp Nodes	13
3.1.1 Database Nodes Palette	13
3.1.2 Analytics Workbench Node Palette.....	17
3.1.3 The Workflow Interface visualization from the DSS Dashboard	17
4 Dashboard Interface.....	19
4.1 Model Builder Interaction	22
5 DSS Deployment.....	25
5.1 Installation Using Docker.....	25
5.2 Installation using Kubernetes	26
6 Next Steps	28
7 Conclusions.....	29
List of Acronyms.....	30

Table of Figures

Figure 1: DSS internal architecture	7
Figure 2: User interaction with the DSS	8
Figure 3: User login interface	8
Figure 4: iHelp platform architecture.....	10
Figure 5: Workflow example	11
Figure 6: Configuration dialog for a function node	11
Figure 7: Node-RED editor interface	12
Figure 8: Node-RED sidebar	13
Figure 9: Database palette	13
Figure 10: Connection node configuration edit dialog.....	14
Figure 11: Select node configuration edit dialog	15
Figure 12: Join node configuration edit dialog.....	16
Figure 13: Database palette package.json file	16
Figure 14: Analytic Workbench palette.....	17
Figure 15: iHelp Workflow interface	18
Figure 16: K-means workflow.....	18
Figure 17: K-means results chart.....	18
Figure 18: Dashboard panel of the sidebar of the Node-RED editor	19
Figure 19: Dashboard layout editor	19
Figure 20: UI-Chart node configuration edit dialog	20
Figure 21: Physician wireframe example	21
Figure 22: Physician DSS Dashboard example.....	21
Figure 23: Dashboard definition and button widget addition example.....	22
Figure 24: Button widget node configuration edit dialog	23
Figure 25: Dashboard and widget creation example	23
Figure 26: Simple workflow creation and results visualization interaction diagram	24
Figure 27: Export workflow or dashboard.....	25

Executive summary

This deliverable reports the work that has been done in the context of T4.3 - “Clinical Decision Support System (DSS), with Visual Analytic Tools”. The main objective of this task to design and implement the decision support visualization component of the iHelp platform. On top of this, the ultimate goal of the DSS is to allow different stakeholders to run analytic functions and visualize analytic results in order to support and decision and policy making.

This task started in the fourth month (M4) of the project, thus this deliverable presents the results achieved during these first eight months of this task. In this context, a prototype of the DSS component has been designed and initially implemented. The DSS prototype allows the definition of dashboards to visualize analytic results, the definition of analytic workflows and visualization of stored data by defining queries with low code. In addition, the DSS implementation is based on Node-RED, a browser-based editor for defining data flows by connecting predefined nodes, hence it follows the same principles. During the next months of the project this prototype will be enhanced taking into account all the requirements of the pilots in the iHelp project and integrated with the rest of iHelp components. To this end, at M22 the second prototype of the DSS will be presented in the context of D4.7 - “iHelp DSS suite with visual analytics II”, and at M32 the final version of the DSS will be reported in the context of D4.8 - “iHelp DSS suite with visual analytics III”.

1 Introduction

This deliverable, D4.6 - “iHelp DSS Suite with Visual Analytics I”, describes the initial version of the iHelp DSS component. The iHelp DSS component will be the iHelp platform interface used by model builders, clinicians, and policy makers as a decision-making process system. The DSS architecture consists of three sub-components: the User login component, the Workflow interface and the Dashboard interface. The DSS is integrated with the iHelp Storage, the iHelp Analytics Workbench, the Predictor and Risk identifiers and the Personalized Predictor components. The main component of the DSS is the Workflow interface component. This component allows the creation of analytical workflows, dashboards for the different types of users and the incremental design of SQL queries while the results of the query are visualized.

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the initial version of the Decision Support System component developed under the scopes of T4.3 - “Clinical DSS Suite with Visual Analytic Tools”. More specifically, this deliverable describes the internal structure of the DSS, the use of the DSS and how it can be deployed.

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

This document is structured as follows: Section 1 introduces the deliverable and its main objectives, Section 2 introduces the architecture and objectives of the DSS component and its interaction with the rest of the iHelp components. Then, Sections 3 and 4 introduce the DSS sub-components. Moreover, Section 5 presents the deployment of the DSS both locally and remotely using Docker and Kubernetes. Finally, Section 6 introduces future work and Section 7 concludes the deliverable.

2 Clinical DSS Suite

This section describes the DSS component in the iHelp project, its objectives, internal architecture, and the interaction with other iHelp components.

2.1 Overview

The DSS component is the user interface and access point to the iHelp platform. Several functionalities allow clinicians/medical experts and policy makers to make decisions based on iHelp data analysis. The DSS provides query building, analytics and visualization mechanisms to access the iHelp data and present them to iHelp users in a friendly way that helps in understanding the iHelp platform's decision models. Technical users – the *model builders* – will find the required tools to design different dashboard for clinicians/medical experts and policy makers, where data will be visualized. The model builder will use a palette of SQL-like, analytic and visualization operators that will allow the creation of pipelines/workflows of transformations and visualizations over the results of the analytical algorithms.

2.2 Overall Objectives

The objectives of T4.3 - “Clinical DSS Suite with Visual Analytic Tools” can be summarized in four different points. First, the DSS has to display iHelp data and analytical algorithm results in customized dashboards to help clinicians/medical experts and policy makers with the decision-making process. Second, provide different operator palettes to provide all: SQL-like, analytic and visualization required functionalities. Third, provide a pipeline/workflow design interface to allow model builder users the creation of the desired decision support dashboards. And fourth, include a user login access point that gives access to the different users to the workflow and/or dashboard interfaces.

2.3 Internal Architecture

The DSS has three well differentiated sub-components: the *User login*, the *Query-builder* and *Workflow*, and the *Dashboard* interfaces. Figure 1 depicts the DSS internal architecture and the relation among the sub-components.

The *User login* interface provides the DSS users the access point for different user types. This interface is in charge of user authentication. Currently, there are three types of users: model builders (data scientists), clinicians/medical experts and policy makers. The User login interface gives access to the functionalities the DSS provides. The functionality available in the DSS will be different depending on the type of user that logs into the system.

The *Workflow* interface provides to data scientists (model builders) users the visual tools for building models that process the data and ways to query the stored data. For that purpose, the workflow presents a palette of available operations and a workspace where SQL-like queries and workflows can be defined by dragging and dropping operators. The operators in the palette implement access to the iHelp data store, analytics, and prediction components available in the iHelp platform. The main users of the workflow interface are data scientists.

The *Dashboard* interface sub-component allows the creation of customized dashboards to show the iHelp data and the results of applying the models and analytics. The dashboards present those results using different chart types and tables. The dashboard's main users are clinicians and policy makers.

Both the Workflow and the Dashboard interface access external components: Analytics Workbench, iHelp storage, Predictor and Risk Identifier, and Personalized Predictor in order to either define the data processing pipeline or model (Workflow) or show the results of the execution of that model.

Figure 1: DSS internal architecture

2.3.1 User Interaction with the DSS

The interaction of a user with the DSS is presented in Figure 2. First, the user must access the DSS through the Login interface. Based on the privileges of the user, the DSS will give access only to the Dashboard interface in case the user is identified as a physician/clinician or policy maker, or to the Dashboard interface and the Query-builder and Workflow interface if the user is a data scientist. The access to the platform is done through the user login interface shown in Figure 3. Users are registered in the iHelp platform assigning a roll: physician/clinician, policy maker or data scientist. The data scientist (model builder in the figure) user will design the workflows and the dashboards that will be used by physicians/clinicians or policy maker users. The Query-builder and Workflow interface interacts with the iHelp storage reading the data and injecting them into the Analytical models provided by the Analytics Workbench or into the Predictor and Risk Identifier or the Personalized Predictor components. The model builder can create dashboards through the Dashboard interface which will show the results of the models and queries designed in the Workflow interface.

Figure 2: User interaction with the DSS

Figure 3: User login interface

2.4 Related Work

With the increasing interest in the field of data science, several tools have emerged to help in the definition of analytics processes and visualize the associated results. Some of the available tools are more oriented to the creation of workflows for accessing data from databases and to be used as input datasets for the execution of analytical algorithms by just drag and dropping different types of nodes and wiring them together. Other tools are more oriented to visualize the data and the results obtained from the execution of the analytical algorithms. More specifically, some of the most well-known and widely used workflow-oriented tools are: Rete¹, Apache Airflow², Node-RED³ and Apache Superset⁴. Rete is a modular framework

¹ <https://rete.js.org/#/>

² <https://airflow.apache.org/>

³ <https://nodered.org/>

⁴ <https://superset.apache.org/>

developed at MIT that allows the creation of flows in a web browser. This framework, which is integrated with Angular⁵, requires to code the logic of the different nodes and the interactions between the wired nodes. Apache Airflow is a platform that allows the creation of workflows as direct acyclic graphs of tasks. These workflows support scheduling and deploying tasks among nodes of a cluster, providing integration with several cloud infrastructures like AWS⁶ and Google Cloud⁷. The main drawback of the Apache Airflow tool is the large learning curve and the complexity of its deployment. Node-RED is a workflow web browser-based editor. It is backed by a large community that creates and shares custom created nodes to be used in the design of workflows. Node-RED provides a dashboard creation interface that allows the design of dashboards using nodes and the visualization of results produced by the workflows using different visualization widgets embedded in the dynamic dashboards. Apache Superset is the successor of the Apache Airflow enhanced with a data visualization interface that allows the creation of customizable dashboards. The learning curve and deployment complexity are the major drawbacks of this tool.

Some of the most popular data visualization tools are: Grafana⁸, Tableau Public⁹, Stashboard¹⁰ and Freeboard¹¹. Grafana allows the visualization of data collected from different databases like Prometheus¹², Graphite¹³, InfluxDB¹⁴ and PostgreSQL¹⁵. Grafana allows the creation of dynamic dashboards and the installation of several plugins that allow the incorporation of different visualization widgets to the available ones. Tableau Public is a tool for data visualization and business analytics. It allows the creation of public dashboards and requires a license to create private ones. Due to that, the usability of this tool is limited in its free version. Finally, Stashboard and Freeboard were created to monitor IoT devices. Stashboard has a very limited visualization set of widgets, while Freeboard has a wide set of visualization widgets, but it requires a license to make created dashboards private.

For the implementation of iHelp's DSS the Node-RED tool was selected to be utilized for several reasons. First, it is fully open source and also has a great community that contributes with the development of visualization widgets that fit with the requirements of the iHelp platform. Second, it is very well documented. This is a fundamental aspect for the DSS development. Third, it has a specific module for the creation and design of dashboards with visualization widgets that can be integrated as part of the analytical workflows. Fourth, the learning curve is small. The customized nodes are created providing JavaScript files. Last but not least, the installation and deployment are much easier in comparison with other tools.

⁵ <https://angular.io/>

⁶ https://aws.amazon.com/es/?nc2=h_lg&aws-products-analytics.sort-by=item.additionalFields.productNameLowercase&aws-products-analytics.sort-order=asc&aws-products-business-apps.sort-by=item.additionalFields.productNameLowercase&aws-products-business-apps.sort-order=asc

⁷ https://cloud.google.com/gcp/?hl=es&utm_source=google&utm_medium=cpc&utm_campaign=emea-es-all-es-bkws-all-all-trial-e-gcp-1010042&utm_content=text-ad-none-any-DEV_c-CRE_495030365279-ADGP_Hybrid%20%7C%20BKWS%20-%20EXA%20%7C%20Txt%20~%20GCP%20~%20General%23

⁸ <https://grafana.com/>

⁹ <https://public.tableau.com/en-us/s/>

¹⁰ <https://www.stashboard.org/>

¹¹ <https://freeboard.io/>

¹² <https://prometheus.io/>

¹³ <https://graphiteapp.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.influxdata.com/>

¹⁵ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

2.5 Positioning and Relation with Other Components

The DSS component is the user entry point to the iHelp platform. The iHelp platform architecture diagram, represented in Figure 4, shows the relations of the DSS component, highlighted in a blue circle, with the rest of the iHelp components, namely the Big Data Platform, developed under the scopes of T4.4 - “Big Data Platform and Knowledge Management System”, the Analytic Workbench, developed under the scopes of T4.2 - “Model Library: Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models”, and the Predictor and Risk identifier and the Personalized Predictor, developed under the scopes of T5.1 - “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”.

Figure 4: iHelp platform architecture

3 Workflow Interface

The Workflow interface sub-component allows the model builder user to design analytics pipelines/workflows, to incrementally design queries for accessing the iHelp data store as well as to design the visualization dashboards for the rest of non-technical users of the platform. This component is based on the Node-RED low code programming tool. Node-RED was created to help users to program by wiring nodes available in different palettes. Nodes in Node-RED is the basic building block of a workflow that process the data received from the previous node/nodes. For instance, Figure 5 shows a simple workflow example using three different types of nodes: one inject node (grey node), one function node (light orange) and one debug node (green). The *inject* node (titled timestamp in the figure) is used for manual triggering the workflow execution. That is, when the node is clicked, a message is produced and sent to the next node. The *function* node executes JavaScript code, for instance parses timestamp of the message received from the previous inject node to HH:MM:SS format and sends the processed timestamp message to the debug node. The debug node displays messages in the *Debug sidebar* within the Node-RED editor.

Figure 5: Workflow example

All nodes can be configured through a configuration node edit dialog that appears by clicking on the node. Figure 6 shows the configuration dialog of the function node. Different parameters can be updated in the configuration dialog. In this case the name of the node, *test function*, is included and the JavaScript code is included here.

Figure 6: Configuration dialog for a function node

The core nodes palette¹⁶ includes a default set of basic nodes for creating workflows. These nodes are *inject*, *debug*, *function*, *change*, *switch* and *template*. The change node can be used to modify message's properties, the switch node allows to send messages to different branches of the workflow and the template node to generate text using messages to fill a template. The core nodes palette can be extended by importing available palettes or creating custom palettes.

Figure 7: Node-RED editor interface

Figure 7 shows the Node-RED editor interface, on the left part the different palettes and their nodes are shown. The sidebar on the right part of the editor interface provides different tools within the editor to obtain information about the different workflows and nodes used and to access the debug console among others. The workspace placed in the central part is the workflow editor which allows the design of workflows by dragging nodes from the palette and wiring them together.

The *sidebar* (Figure 8) includes different panels like the information panel, the node's help panel, the *debug messages* for showing the values of the different messages generated during a workflow execution and the *configuration nodes* panel. The *context data* panel shows the contents of the context when a workflow is executed, that is the messages sent between the different nodes. And the Dashboard panel is used for the creation of the dashboards. This Dashboard panel appears when the Node-RED dashboard nodes palette is installed.

¹⁶ <https://nodered.org/docs/user-guide/nodes>

Figure 8: Node-RED sidebar

3.1 iHelp Nodes

Two different node palettes have been designed and implemented to satisfy the iHelp platform requirements: the *Database* and *Analytic Workbench* palettes. The creation of custom Node-RED palettes was done according to the node-RED documentation¹⁷. Three types of files are needed in the folder of each palette: one JSON file named `package.json`, and as many JavaScript and HTML files as nodes in the palette. The `package.json` file provides the information of the palette: the name and the description of the palette and the nodes that belongs to that concrete palette. The JavaScript files stores the logic of the nodes, and the HTML files provide the configuration dialog implementation. In the following section the different palettes and nodes created within the context of the iHelp project are described.

3.1.1 Database Nodes Palette

The Database palette contains the nodes used for the creation of the SQL queries by means of drag and dropping the database operators in the Node-RED workspace. That is, the creation of queries following the low code model of Node-RED: At this stage of the project the database nodes available in the palette are *Connection*, *Select*, and *Join* nodes as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Database palette

¹⁷ <https://nodered.org/docs/creating-nodes/>

The *connection node* is used to select the table that is going to be accessed. The configuration panel of this node, presented in Figure 10, has the configuration node edit dialog where the connection to the expected database has to be defined by filling in the information in the fields *Host*, *Port*, *User* and *Password*. Once these fields are filled in, the *Database* and *Table* drop downs show the available databases and the tables of the selected database. Once the database and table are selected this information will be shared with the rest of wired nodes of the workflow.

Figure 10: Connection node configuration edit dialog

The *select node* is used for choosing the relevant columns of the configured table and applying filters over the table. Internally, a select SQL statement is being created. Figure 11 shows the configuration edit dialog of the select node. The left part shows a checkbox with the columns of the table configured in the connection node; it allows to select columns whose data is going to be used. At the time the columns are selected their values are shown in order to help the data scientist in the query building process. In this case the columns *BlockFloor* and *Unavailable* are selected. Just below the list of columns the *QueryPreview* section displays the two columns and the first five rows in the table with only those columns. Additionally, there are two checkboxes to include the *distinct* and *count* options to the SQL select statement.

Another menu is used for configuring the *where* clause in a select statement (right part of Figure 11). For each new where clause a new line appears to concatenate different clauses by means of “AND” and “OR” logical operators. Each line has two fields, the first one is a dropdown menu that shows the columns of the table and the second one is a text box component to define the predicate used in the where clause. *Order by* and *limit* clauses are included to indicate how to sort the results and the maximum number of rows to be returned.

Figure 11: Select node configuration edit dialog

A similar menu and procedure are used for the definition of join statements being implemented by the *join* node. In this case the configuration node edit dialog (Figure 12) needs data from the two tables to be joined, room and floor tables in the figure. Tables' properties are received from the two different connection nodes, one per table. The left table to be joined, the room table, is configured by selecting the columns of interest (*RoomNumber*). At this point the values of up to five rows are displayed. A second table is also selected to be joined with the previous one, the block table. Columns *FloorBlock* and *BlockCode* are selected, and the corresponding rows are then displayed. The *On* menu is used to indicate the column from which the join has to be performed. For instance, the join SQL statement that corresponds to Figure 12 is:

```
SELECT room.BlockFloor, block.BlockFloor, block.BlockCode
FROM room
JOIN block ON room.BlockFloor = block.BlockFloor;
```


Figure 12: Join node configuration edit dialog

The *Database* palette is implemented by adding a folder with seven files: the *package.json* file, three JavaScript files and three HTML files, two per node. Figure 13 shows the content of the *package.json* file where the palette and the nodes are defined. In the *package.json* file one can configure the name of the package that contains the nodes, the version of the nodes, the description of the palette, the script to test the nodes in case there is any test, the keywords that defines the palette, the author, the type of license and the nodes. Each node is added to the *nodes* label, being the key, the name of the node and the value is the code that is executed by that node. In the figure the nodes are *Connection*, *Select* and *Join*. The code for each node is in the files: *connection.js*, *select.js* and *join.js*.

```

{
  "name": "iHelp Database",
  "version": "1.2.0",
  "description": "iHelp Database nodes",
  "main": "none",
  "scripts": {
    "test": "echo \"Error: no test specified\" && exit 1"
  },
  "keywords": [
    "iHelp",
    "db"
  ],
  "author": "UPM",
  "license": "ISC",
  "node-red": {
    "nodes": {
      "Connection": "connection.js",
      "Select": "select.js",
      "Join": "join.js"
    }
  }
}

```

Figure 13: Database palette package.json file

3.1.2 Analytics Workbench Node Palette

The analytic workbench platform is based on DRYICE (short name for ICE Knowledge Discovery)¹⁸. Several clustering algorithms are available for processing the iHelp data: K-means, BIRCH (Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering using Hierarchies) and Ward's Method. DRYICE is designed to allow the deployment of models defined as one or more docker containers, instantiated via a Docker compose file. The algorithms run inside these containers, receive data, process, and forward the result to the next component. It uses Kafka environment variables to specify how messages are passed down the chain. The messages being passed can either be data or signals that data is ready.

The DSS hides the implementation and configuration of the Analytics Workbench executed on DRYICE by providing different analytics nodes. These nodes are configured so that when a workflow that triggers their execution is run, the corresponding invocation is sent to the workbench. This communication is internally managed by the DSS by sending Kafka messages. Each node will prepare the required Kafka message for one of the analytical algorithms, configure the required data and being informed on where the output will be available to collect the result. Figure 14 shows the analytics nodes available in the Analytics Workbench palette. Each node represents one of the three available analytics algorithms, e.g., k-means, BIRCH and Ward's method.

Figure 14: Analytic Workbench palette

3.1.3 The Workflow Interface visualization from the DSS Dashboard

The iHelp workflow interface is presented in Figure 15. Note that the Node-RED editor interface is embedded into the DSS and connected with it. This interface allows the model builder to observe the data stored in the iHelp storage by creating SQL like query flows with the database palette nodes and preview the results of each node in the table presented below the Node-RED editor interface. This table changes dynamically, this means that when a new database node is added to the flow, the table preview the result of the composed SQL query till this moment.

¹⁸ <https://drydev.icelab.cloud/docs/#!/index.md>

Figure 15: iHelp Workflow interface

It is possible to create workflows that include database nodes and analytics nodes and store the results again in the iHelp storage. Figure 16 shows a complete workflow where data from the table *room of the hospital* database in the iHelp storage is used for doing a K-means clustering. After the clustering algorithm completes, the results will be available in the iHelp dashboard. In this case the results of the K-means algorithm are sent from the K-means node to the chart node. This node displays the result in a chart where the data is grouped. An example of the chart generated is shown in Figure 17 below.

Figure 16: K-means workflow

Figure 17: K-means results chart

All created query flows and analytical workflows are stored in the Node-RED internal storage and can be reused.

4 Dashboard Interface

The dashboard interface is used for presenting the results of workflows and queries to different types of users. The Node-RED Dashboard module¹⁹ allows the creation of live dashboards using different nodes from its palette. The dashboard panel of the sidebar in the Node-RED editor is used for the definition of the layout of the dashboards. Figure 18 shows a screenshot of the dashboard panel where two different dashboards, Login and DB workflow, are defined. The Login dashboard has a layout called Group 1 and the DB workflow dashboard has two layouts, Database and Tables, and Selected table data. Layouts are sections of the dashboard where the different visualization widgets (table, charts, buttons, dropdown lists, etc.) can be set. Figure 19 shows the layout editor of the DB workflow dashboard, this editor appears when the DB workflow dashboard is select from the Dashboard panel of the sidebar. In the example of the Figure 19, the two layouts are shown as grids defining the area that each layout is going to occupy in the dashboard. The layout named *Database and Tables* contains two dropdown widgets and one button widget, while the *Selected table data* contains a table widget.

Figure 18: Dashboard panel of the sidebar of the Node-RED editor

Figure 19: Dashboard layout editor

Some of the Dashboard palette available nodes are:

- `ui_button`: Adds a button widget to the layout.
- `ui_dropdown`: Adds a dropdown list widget to select an option.
- `ui_switch`: Adds a switch widget to the layout.
- `ui-slider`: Adds a slider widget where several options can be added to select.
- `ui_numeric`: Shows a number in the dashboard.
- `ui_text_input`: Adds text to the payload message in the flow.
- `ui_date_picker`: Shows a calendar and allows to pick a date or range of dates.
- `ui_colour_picker`: Color selection.
- `ui_form`: Adds a customized form to the dashboard.

¹⁹ <https://flows.nodered.org/node/node-red-dashboard>

- ui_text: Adds unmodifiable text to the dashboard.
- ui_gauge: Adds a gauge widget to the dashboard.
- ui_chart: Adds a chart to the dashboard.
- ui_audio: Allows to include audio to the dashboard

The ui_form, ui_text_input and ui_date_picker nodes are used to provide information to the Node-RED editor to be used in the workflow's creation. The rest of nodes are used for presenting the results produced by the SQL queries and analytical workflows in the dashboard. The ui_chart node configuration edit dialog is used for selecting the type of chart for displaying the results. The charts available currently are: line chart, bar chart, pie chart, polar area chart and radar chart. Figure 20 shows the UI-Chart configuration node edit dialog with the available chart types listed.

Figure 20: UI-Chart node configuration edit dialog

Figure 21 shows a dashboard wireframe designed in the context of T2.4 - "User Centred Design". Figure 22 shows this wireframe implemented in the DSS showing the information of patients, his or her medical history and the result of different analytical models that help the clinician to evaluate the risk of having pancreatic cancer. In the development of this dashboard the ui_text, ui_dropdown, ui_switch, ui_table, ui_chart, ui_buttons and ui_data_picker nodes have been used.

Figure 21: Physician wireframe example

Figure 22: Physician DSS Dashboard example

4.1 Model Builder Interaction

This section presents the interaction diagrams for creating dashboards and workflows and the visualization of results within a visualization widget in a previously created dashboard.

When the model builder creates a dashboard for a physician/clinician or policy maker user, he starts creating a panel tab from the Dashboard panel of the sidebar and creates a group in the created panel tab. The group allows include widgets and define their location in the dashboard. Once the group is created the user can drag and drop a button widget node into the Node-RED editor, access the configuration node edit dialog and assigns the button to the created group, selecting the group name from the dropdown list that appears, as shown in Figure 24. Finally, the user clicks the deploy button of the Node-RED editor and the new dashboard is deployed and accessible from the web browser, (Figure 25). The whole interaction is depicted in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Dashboard definition and button widget addition example

Figure 24: Button widget node configuration edit dialog

Figure 25: Dashboard and widget creation example

Next interaction diagram depicted in Figure 26 shows the creation of a workflow and the visualization of the result using a chart widget node. First of all, the model builder user drags and drops different nodes. For instance, an iHelp connection node to establish the connection with the iHelp storage, a select node to read the data used as the input data set for the K-Means algorithm and finally a chart widget node as shown in Figure 16. Then, all nodes must be configured. The connection node establishes the connection with the iHelp storage and is used for selecting a database and table. The select node has to be configured to retrieve all required information from the tables configured in the connection node. Next, the K-Means node is configured trigger the execution of the K-Means algorithm. Finally, the chart node must be configured with the dashboard and group it belongs to, the title, chart type and the rest of configuration available from the chart node configuration edit dialog. Then, the model builder clicks the deploy button of the Node-RED editor and the dashboard will be deployed with the configured chart and the result of the K-Means algorithm.

Meanwhile, internally the DSS workflow interface will access the data from the iHelp storage and will invoke the K-Means algorithm with the retrieved data set. Finally, the result of the K-Means algorithm will be shown in the chart.

Figure 26: Simple workflow creation and results visualization interaction diagram

5 DSS Deployment

This section describes how the DSS is installed and deployed. First of all, the description of a local deployment for testing purposes is presented and then, the production deployment is presented.

5.1 Installation Using Docker

The iHelp DSS component release is available from the project Gitlab repository. All members of the consortium have access to the Gitlab repository and should be able to download the release from it with the command:

```
git clone https://gitlab.ihelp-project.eu/ainhoa/ihelp-dss.git
```

Once the distribution is downloaded, the system administrator has to create the local docker image with all created nodes. This docker image will deploy the DSS in a containerized environment. The command to create the docker image is:

```
cd ihelp-dss
docker build -t ihelp-dss .
```

With the image ready, the system administrator can deploy the DSS locally in the docker environment with the following command:

```
docker run -d -p 0.0.0.0:1880:1880 --name ihelp-dss ihelp-dss
```

This command will start a container called ihelp-dss where the DSS is running and exports the port 1880 to access the DSS workflow and dashboards interfaces. The DSS is available in any browser by typing <http://localhost:1880> to access the Node-RED editor and <http://localhost:1880/ui> to access the Dashboards. This type of installation is only recommended for testing purposes. Any workflows and dashboards created are deleted when the container is stopped. In order to save locally the created workflows and dashboards it is possible to export them through the Node-RED editor clicking on the menu at the upper left part and clicking on the Export option as it is shown in Figure 27. This will generate a JSON file that can be stored in the user's machine and this JSON file can be imported again once the container is deployed.

Figure 27: Export workflow or dashboard

5.2 Installation using Kubernetes

The release can be installed using a container orchestrator like Kubernetes. This installation will be used in production. It is required to have a docker registry service available in order to publish the docker image of the DSS. The system administrator will publish the docker image by issuing these commands:

```
docker build -t {name of the docker registry}/ihelp-dss .
docker push {name of the docker registry}/ihelp-dss
```

The DSS stores the workflows and dashboards in a persistent volume that must be created before the DSS is deployed. An example of a persistent volume creation is shown below. The YAML file indicates the amount of resources, 1Gb of disc in this case. All data stored in this P.V.C will remain across different deployments of the DSS. This file can be found in the git project folder in the file with name of dss-storage-pvc.yml.

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: dss-storage-pvc
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  storageClassName: ebs-sc
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 1Gi
```

To create the PVC once the storage resources have been set, the system administrator will use the following command:

```
Kubectl apply -f dss-storage-pvc.yml
```

Once the Persistent Volume Claim (PVC) has been configured it is possible to deploy the DSS using a Kubernetes component. The dss-deployment.yml file needed is shown below and can be found in the downloaded git project.

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: ihelp-dss
  labels:
    app: ihelp-dss
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: ihelp-dss
  updateStrategy:
    type: RollingUpdate
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: ihelp-dss
    spec:
      containers:
        - image: {name of the docker registry}/ihelp-dss:latest
          name: dss
          ports:
            - containerPort: 1880
          volumeMounts:
```

```
- name: dss-storage
  mountPath: /dss/
startupProbe:
  exec:
    command:
      - /bin/sh
      - -c
      - node-red
  timeoutSeconds: 5
  failureThreshold: 30
  periodSeconds: 10
resources:
  limits:
    cpu: 4000m
    memory: 4Gi
  requests:
    cpu: 2000m
    memory: 2Gi
env:
- name: USEIP
  value: "yes"
restartPolicy: Always
imagePullSecrets:
- name: registrysecret
volumes:
- name: dss-storage
  persistentVolumeClaim:
    claimName: dss-storage-pvc
```

This deployment controller file creates a replica of the DSS service and configures it to be deployed in a node of the cluster Kubernetes labelled as “app: ihelp-dss”. The required resources are configured to 2000m of CPU and 2Gb of memory and sets a limit of 4000m of CPU and 4Gb of memory. Moreover, the previously created PVC is configured to be used by the DSS service. In order to deploy the DSS the system administrator will issue this command:

```
Kubect1 apply -f dss-deployment.yml
```

6 Next Steps

Throughout this deliverable we have presented the DSS component, developed in the context of T4.3 - “Clinical DSS Suite with Visual Analytic Tools”. At this stage of the project, we have defined the internal architecture of the DSS and we have developed the main required nodes. A second version of this deliverable is foreseen to be delivered in M22 of the project, in the context of D4.7 - “iHelp DSS suite with visual analytics II”, that will include a revised version and implementation of the DSS. The final design and implementation of the DSS will be reported under the scopes of D4.8 - “iHelp DSS suite with visual analytics III” at M32.

Moreover, the integration with the DRyICE platform, developed in the context of T4.2 - “Model Library: Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models”, should include other analytics that will be of interest for the project. The integration of the prediction algorithms, developed under the scopes of T5.1 - “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”, and the DSS will also be implemented. Finally, the evaluation of the integration with the iHelp storage as well with the rest components of the iHelp platform needs to be completed.

Regarding the implementation of the different dashboards, we will give support to the model builder users in order to design and create the needed dashboards for the physicians/clinicians and policy makers and improve the available tools if needed based on that feedback.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the Clinical DSS Suite with Visual Analytic Tools component of the iHelp project. The DSS helps clinicians and policy makers during the decision-making process by providing customizable dashboards with different charts and other information that the analytics tools and risk identification algorithms will produce. This component uses the different analytical models, designed in the context of T5.1 - “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”, to predict and identify the risk of each patient to develop Pancreatic Cancer and to decide the usage of different treatments in case of already diagnosed Pancreatic Cancer patients.

List of Acronyms

ATC	Athens Technology Centre
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CA	Consortium Agreement
CPU	Central Processing Unit
D	Deliverable
DB	Database
DoA	Description of Action
DSS	Decision Support System
EU	European Union
Gb	Gigabyte
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
ICE	Information Catalyst for Enterprise
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LXS	LeanXcale
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
PVC	Persistent Volume Claim
SQL	Structured Query Language
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Centre